

CORRECTION OF SECOND ORDER LIGHT FOR THE HICO™ SENSOR ONBOARD THE INTERNATIONAL SPACE SATATION

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ABSTRACT

The Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean (HICO™) [1] is a new spaceborne sensor designed specifically for monitoring the turbid coastal waters and large inland lakes and rivers from the International Space Station (ISS). HICO™ is now collecting hyperspectral imaging data in the wavelength range of 0.4 – 1.0 micron with a spatial resolution of approximately 90 meters and a spectral resolution of 5.7 nanometers. During the construction of the HICO™ instrument, it was not possible to place a blocking filter in front of the CCD (Charge-coupled device) array located in the focal plane. As a result, the second order light from the shorter visible spectral region falls onto the detectors covering the near-IR spectral region above 0.8 micron. In order to have accurate radiometric calibrations of the near-IR channels, the second order light effects need to be removed. Through analysis of HICO™ imaging data containing features of shallow underwater objects, such as coral reef, we have developed a new empirical technique to correct for the second order light effects. HICO™ data acquired over Midway Island, Key Largo, Bahamas Bay and Philippine Sea are used to demonstrate the effectiveness of the new technique.

Index Terms— Imaging Spectrometer, HICO™, Hyperspectral imager, Coastal water, Remote Sensing, Second order light correction

1. INTRODUCTION

The Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean (HICO™) sensor is the first spaceborne imaging spectrometer designed specifically for remote sensing of the complex coastal environment. The sensor was built at the Naval Research Laboratory in Washington DC. It was launched into space with a Japanese HII-B rocket from Tanegashima Space Center, Japan on September 11, 2009 and docked onto the International Space Station (ISS) on September 24, 2009. HICO™ is now collecting useful hyperspectral imaging data in the wavelength range of 0.4

– 1.0 micron with a spatial resolution of approximately 90 meters and a spectral resolution of 5.7 nanometers. The actual spectral range covered by HICO is from 0.35 micron to 1.08 micron. It is expected that HICO™ data will be studied for better understanding of the global coastal waters as well as certain inland lakes [2].

2. BACKGROUND

When building the HICO™ instrument, it was not feasible to install a filter in front of the detectors to block the second-order light for detectors covering the near-IR spectral region above 0.8 micron. Second order light from the shorter wavelength range in the visible spectral region between 0.4 and 0.5 micron falls in the same spatial pixels as first-order light for the near-IR spectral region between 0.8 and 1.0 micron. As a result, the near-IR channels receive both first order light in the 0.8 – 1.0 micron range and second order light from the 0.4 – 0.5 micron range. In order to recover the true near-IR channel radiances from HICO data, the second order light effect needs to be removed completely from the total radiances received by these near-IR channels.

After the construction of the HICO™ instrument, spatial, spectral, and radiometric calibrations were performed in the calibration lab at the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL). Calibration coefficients were generated from the HICO™ lab data. Applications of these laboratory calibration coefficients to HICO™ data measured from ISS did not result in a complete removal of the second order light effects.

Figure 1 shows examples of ISS HICO™ images acquired over the Bahamas in the Atlantic Ocean on October 22, 2009. Image (a) is the true color RGB image, and images (b), (c), (d), (e), (f), (g) and (h) are single band images at wavelengths of 0.502, 0.600, 0.860, 0.903, 0.955, 1.001 and 1.035 micron, respectively. In the RGB image, the left portions in green and blue colors are shallow water regions, the right portions in black color are deep water areas. A sharp curved line separating the

shallow water areas from deep water areas is seen in this image. The shallow features are also seen in the single band image at $\lambda = 0.502, 0.600$ micron (see Fig. 1b and 1c). Because of the strong liquid water absorption in the near-IR spectral region, the shallow water features disappeared in the 0.86-micron image (see Fig. 1d), as expected. However these features re-appeared in images at longer wavelength channels, starting from $\lambda = 0.90$ micron, and becoming stronger at $\lambda = 0.95$ and 1.035 micron (see Fig. 1e to 1h), due to the second order light effects. In order to obtain the true near-IR channel radiances, the second-order light effects must be removed.

3. METHOD AND SAMPLE RESULTS

Through analysis of ISS HICO™ data acquired over water surfaces with underwater features, such as coral reefs, we have developed an empirical but very effective method for quantifying the second order light effect. This method is based on the fact that, if the second order light effects are not present, spatial features of coral reefs and other objects in shallow water areas should not be observed in images of narrow channels near 1 micron. This is because

the 1-micron solar radiation transmitted into water is totally absorbed by the water. The observation of spatial features of shallow water objects in 1-micron channel images is an indication of the presence of the second order effects.

We extract a pair of shallow water spectra, $S(\lambda)$, and a deep water spectrum, $D(\lambda)$, from a HICO™ ISS data set for the development of the empirical method. We use $p(\lambda)$ to represent the empirical correction curve for removing the second order light effects.

The basic equation for the derivation of $p(\lambda)$ is

$$S(\lambda) - p(\lambda) * S(\lambda/2) = D(\lambda) - p(\lambda) * D(\lambda/2) \quad (1)$$

- where
- $S(\lambda)$: signal from the shallow water area at λ ;
- $D(\lambda)$: signal from the deep water area at λ ;
- $S(\lambda/2)$: signal from the shallow water area at half wavelength ($\lambda/2$);
- $D(\lambda/2)$: signal from the deep water area at half wavelength ($\lambda/2$);
- $p(\lambda)$: the empirical scaling factor for correcting the second order light. This factor is the fraction of the first order light leaking into the near-IR detector.

Fig. 1. Sample ISS HICO™ images acquired over the Bahamas in the Atlantic Ocean on October 22, 2009. Image (a) is the true color RGB image, and images (b), (c), (d), (e), (f), (g) and (h) are single band images at wavelengths of 0.502, 0.600, 0.860, 0.903, 0.955, 1.001 and 1.035 micron, respectively. Spatial features of shallow water are clearly seen in the left half images, such as in Fig. 1a, 1b and 1c. The black parts in the right half images are the deepwater regions. The white spots in the images are clouds. Image from 1e to 1h show the second order effects of the shallow water in the near IR channels.

The term, $p(\lambda) \cdot S(\lambda/2)$, on the left side of Eq. (1) is the second order signal at the near-IR wavelength λ contributed by the signal at $\lambda/2$ for the shallow water spectrum. Similarly, the term, $p(\lambda) \cdot D(\lambda/2)$, on the right side of Eq. (1) is the second order signal for the deep water spectrum. Eq. (1) means that, after the corrections of second order light effects, the near-IR channel signal over the shallow water area should equal that over the deep water area.

Solving for $p(\lambda)$, Eq. (1) can be re-written as

$$p(\lambda) = [S(\lambda) - D(\lambda)] / [S(\lambda/2) - D(\lambda/2)]. \quad (2)$$

The empirical correction curve can be calculated from the data according to equation (2).

In order to generate the empirical factor for the second order light corrections, we selected a number of pairs of shallow water and deepwater spectra from several HICOTM ISS data sets, including those acquired over - Midway Island, Bahamas Bay, the Philippine Sea, and Key Largo Bay in southern Florida. Figure 2 shows examples of curves as a function of wavelength derived from pairs of water pixels over Midway Island and Bahamas Bay. The results show that the factors are linear functions of wavelength, especially at wavelengths greater than 0.9 micron. At the lower end of wavelengths ($0.86 < \lambda < 0.90 \mu\text{m}$), the scaling factors have relatively larger uncertainties mainly due to much smaller second order light effects, as shown in Fig. 1(e). The black diamonds are the averaged values from all the selected data points. A linear fit to the averaged values gives a correlation coefficient of 0.9985. The black line demonstrates that approximately 1% to 2.5% of the first order light in the visible is leaked into the near-IR detectors.

Fig. 2. Empirical factors as a function of wavelength for second order light corrections.

We have applied the derived empirical curve (see the black line in Fig. 2) to a number of HICOTM data sets for the correction of the second order light effects. Very reasonable results have been obtained.

Figure 3 shows an example of spectral plots for HICOTM data acquired over shallow water and deepwater areas before and after the second-order light removal in digital counts, or digital numbers. The top and middle curves are the shallow water and deepwater spectra without second-order light corrections, respectively. Both curves have extra counts due to the second order light effects. The bottom lines show the second-order light corrected curves for both the shallow-water and deepwater spectra. After the correction, both the shallow water and deepwater spectra above 0.8 micron become identical (the red line in the plot).

Fig. 3. Sample spectra for shallow water and deep water areas before and after second order light corrections.

Figure 4 images from e' through h' correspond to images from e through h in Fig. 1, except that the second order light effects are corrected. The shallow water features seen in the Fig. 1 images have disappeared completely in the Fig. 4 images. This demonstrates that the second order light effects are removed.

Fig. 4. Images corresponding to the Fig. 1 e to h images, except that the second order light effects are corrected. The shallow water features are absent after the corrections.

Fig. 5. Calibrated radiances over a shallow water region before and after the second-order light corrections. The black line is the spectral plot before the second-order correction and the red line is the plot after correction.

The plots in Figure 5 show the spectra of the shallow water before and after second-order light corrections in the radiance unit ($\text{Watt/m}^2/\text{um/sr}$). The black line is the spectrum before the second order corrections. The radiances increased at wavelengths longer than 0.86 μm . This is incorrect since strong liquid water absorptions at these wavelength regions will reduce the strength of the signals, not increase the signals. The red line in the figure 5 is the spectral plot at same pixel as the black line after second-order light corrections. It shows the second-order light effects were removed correctly. After correcting the second order effects, the intensities of the water spectrum decrease as the wavelength increases.

Figure 6 shows another example of second order light corrections. The left plot shows a HICOTM RGB image acquired over the Philippine Sea, the middle one is the 1.0- μm single channel image. The shallow water features are seen near the islands in image. The right one shows

the same image as the middle one, except with the second order light corrections. The shallow water features in this image are hardly seen, indicating that it was properly removed.

Fig. 6. A RGB image (left) over the Philippine Sea with features under shallow waters, the corresponding single channel image before (middle) and after (right) the second-order light corrections at 1.0- μm channel.

4. SUMMARY

Through analysis of HICOTM imaging data containing features of shallow underwater objects, we have developed a new empirical and accurate technique to correct for the second order light effects. The same technique is, in principle, applicable for the correction of second order effects from hyperspectral data measured with other similar sensors without blocking filters, such as the commercially available CASI instruments.

5. REFERENCES

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